

International Journal of Information Technology, Research and Applications (IJITRA)

Chaubey, S.K, Yadav, S.K. & Mahesh Garvandha (2022). Kenmotsu Manifolds Admitting a Non-Symmetric Non-Metric Connection. International Journal of Information Technology, Research and Applications, 1(3), 11-14.

ISSN: 2583 5343

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7384782

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.ijitra.com/index.php/ijitra/issue/archive>

Published by:
PRISMA Publications

IJITRA is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

International Journal of Information Technology, Research and Applications (IJITRA) is a journal that publishes articles which contribute new theoretical results in all the areas of Computer Science, Communication Network and Information Technology. Research paper and articles on Big Data, Machine Learning, IOT, Blockchain, Network Security, Optical Integrated Circuits, and Artificial Intelligence are in prime position.

PRISMA
PUBLICATIONS

<https://www.prismapublications.com/>

Kenmotsu Manifolds Admitting a Non-Symmetric Non-Metric Connection

S. K. Chaubey¹, S. K. Yadav² and Mahesh Garvandha³

^{1,3}Mathematics Section, Department of Information Technology, Shinas College of Technology,
PO Box 77, Postal Code 324 Al Aqur, Shinas, Sultanate of Oman.

²Department of Mathematics, Poornima college of Engineering, Rajasthan, India.

¹sudhakar.chaubey@shct.edu.om;

²prof_sky16@yahoo.com;

³mahesh.garvandha@shct.edu.om

Article Info

Article history:

From the proceedings of 2nd Symposium on Information Technology and Applied Mathematics – SITAM 2019, 6th November 2019.

Host: University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Shinas, Sultanate of Oman.

Keywords:

Kenmotsu manifolds
non-symmetric non-metric
connection
Ricci semi-symmetric manifold
Einstein manifolds

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present paper is to study the properties of Kenmotsu manifolds equipped with a non-symmetric non-metric connection. We also establish some curvature properties of Kenmotsu manifolds. It is proved that a Kenmotsu manifold endowed with a non-symmetric non-metric is irregular.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

S. K. Chaubey
Mathematics Section,
Department of Information Technology,
Shinas College of Technology,
PO Box 77,
Postal Code 324 Al Aqur,
Shinas,
Sultanate of Oman.
sudhakar.chaubey@shct.edu.om

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

A contact metric manifold is capable to resolve many issues of sciences, engineering and medical sciences, and hence it is attracting the researchers to work in this area. Boothby & Wang (1958) started the study of a differentiable manifold with contact and almost contact metric structures. Kenmotsu (1971) introduced a class of almost contact metric manifold and named as Kenmotsu manifold. Since then, the properties of Kenmotsu manifolds have studied by several authors such as De & Pathak (2004), Sinha & Srivastava (1991), Jun, De & Pathak (2005), De, Yildiz and Yaliniz (2008), Chaubey et al. (2010, 2012, 2015, 2018), De (2008), Cihan (2006) and many others.

Let M be a Riemannian manifold associated with the Riemannian metric g . A linear connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ on M is said to be symmetric if the torsion tensor \tilde{T} of $\tilde{\nabla}$ vanishes, otherwise it is non-symmetric. If the torsion tensor \tilde{T} assumes the form $\tilde{T}(X, Y) = \pi(Y)X - \pi(X)Y$ for all vector fields X and Y on M , then then linear connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ is called semi-symmetric connection (Friedmann, & J. A. Schouten, 1924). Moreover, if $\tilde{\nabla}g =$

0 on M then $\bar{\nabla}$ is said to be metric, otherwise non-metric (Agashe & Chafle, 1992). Chaubey & Ojha (2008) defined and studied the properties of non-symmetric non-metric connection on almost contact metric manifolds. The geometrical properties of the same connection have been studied by several authors. We refer (Chaubey & Kumar (2010); Chaubey & De (2019); Chaubey, & Yildiz (2019); Chaubey et al. (2019)) and their references.

Above studies motivate us to study the properties of Kenmotsu manifold equipped with a non-symmetric non-metric connection.

2. PRELIMINARIES:

A smooth manifold M of dimension $(2n+1)$ is said to be an almost contact metric manifold if it admits a $(1, 1)$ tensor field ϕ , $(1, 0)$ type vector field ξ , $(0, 1)$ type vector field η and a compatible metric g of type $(0, 2)$ satisfies

$$\phi^2 = I + \eta \otimes \xi, \quad \eta(\xi) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) - \eta(X)\eta(Y) \quad (2.1)$$

for all X and Y on M (Blair, 1976).

Additionally, if M satisfies

$$\nabla_X \xi = X - \eta(X)\xi \Leftrightarrow (\nabla_X \eta)(Y) = g(X, Y) - \eta(X)\eta(Y) \quad (2.2)$$

for all X on M , then M is said to be a Kenmotsu manifold (1971). Here ∇ denotes the Levi-Civita connection of g . It is observed that the manifold holds the following relations,

$$\eta(R(X, Y)Z) = \eta(Y)g(X, Z) - \eta(X)g(Y, Z), \quad (2.3)$$

$$R(X, Y)\xi = \eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X, \quad (2.4)$$

$$R(\xi, X)Y = \eta(Y)X - g(X, Y)\xi, \quad (2.5)$$

$$S(X, \xi) = -(n-1)\eta(X) \quad (2.6)$$

for all X, Y and Z on M (Kenmotsu (1971), Chaubey & Ojha (2010), Chaubey & R. H. Ojha (2012)). Here R and S denote the Riemannian curvature and Ricci tensors of g , respectively.

A Kenmotsu manifold M is said to be η -Einstein if the non-vanishing Ricci tensor S satisfies the relation $S(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + b\eta(X)\eta(Y)$ for all X and Y on M , where a and b are smooth functions on M (Kenmotsu (1971)).

3. NON-SYMMETRIC NON-METRIC CONNECTION

Let M be a Kenmotsu manifold of dimension $(2n+1)$. A linear connection $\bar{\nabla}$ on M , defined by

$$\bar{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y - \eta(Y)X - g(X, Y)\xi \quad (3.1)$$

for all vector fields X and Y on M , is known as a non-symmetric non-metric connection (De & Pathak (2004)), if the torsion tensor \bar{T} of $\bar{\nabla}$ takes the form $\bar{T}(X, Y) = \pi(X)Y - \pi(Y)X$ and

$$(\bar{\nabla}_X g)(Y, Z) = 2\eta(Y)g(X, Z) + 2\eta(Z)g(X, Y). \quad (3.2)$$

In consequence of the equations (2.1), (2.3) and (3.1), we get

$$\bar{\nabla}_X \xi = \nabla_X \xi - X - \eta(X)\xi = -2\eta(X)\xi. \quad (3.3)$$

If \bar{R} denotes the Riemannian curvature tensor with respect to $\bar{\nabla}$, then it relates to R by the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z - \beta(X, Z)Y + \beta(Y, Z)X - g(Y, Z)(\nabla_X \xi - \eta(X)\xi) \\ &\quad + g(Y, Z)(\nabla_Y \xi - \eta(Y)\xi), \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

where β is tensor field of type $(0, 2)$ and defined as

$$\beta(X, Y) = (\nabla_X \eta)(Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y) + g(X, Y) = 2g(X, Y). \quad (3.5)$$

In view of (3.5), equation (3.4) takes the form

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = R(X, Y)Z + g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y + 2[g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)]\xi. \quad (3.6)$$

Contracting equation (3.6) along the vector field X , we lead

$$\bar{S}(Y, Z) = S(Y, Z) + 2(n+1)g(Y, Z) - 2\eta(Y)\eta(Z), \quad (3.7)$$

which gives

$$\bar{Q}Y = QY + 2(n+1)Y - 2\eta(Y)\xi. \quad (3.8)$$

The contraction of (3.8) gives

$$\bar{\gamma} = \gamma + 2n(2n+3). \quad (3.9)$$

Here $\bar{\gamma}$ and γ are the scalar curvatures with respect to $\bar{\nabla}$ and ∇ , respectively. \bar{Q} and Q denote the Ricci operators corresponding to the Ricci tensors \bar{S} and S with respect to $\bar{\nabla}$ and ∇ , respectively.

Setting $Z = \xi$ in (3.7) and then using the equations (2.1) and (2.4), we obtain

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi = R(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y + 2[\eta(Y)\eta(X) - \eta(X)\eta(Y)]\xi = 0.$$

This shows that the Kenmotsu manifold M is irregular ($\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi = 0$) with respect to $\bar{\nabla}$. Thus we state:

Theorem 3.1. Every $(2n+1)$ -dimensional Kenmotsu manifold equipped with $\bar{\nabla}$ is irregular with respect to $\bar{\nabla}$.

4. RICCI SEMI-SYMMETRIC KENMOTSU MANIFOLD WITH A NON-SYMMETRIC NON-METRIC CONNECTION

This section deals with the study of Ricci semi-symmetric Kenmotsu manifold equipped with a non-symmetric non-metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$. It is well known that

$$(\bar{R}(X, Y) \cdot \bar{S})(Z, U) = -\bar{S}(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z, U) - \bar{S}(Z, \bar{R}(X, Y)U).$$

In view of (2.1) and (3.7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{R}(X, Y) \cdot \bar{S})(Z, U) &= (R(X, Y) \cdot S)(Z, U) - g(Y, Z)S(X, U) \\ &- 2(n+1)g(Y, Z)g(X, U) + g(X, Z)S(Y, U) + 2\eta(Y)\eta(Z)g(X, Z)g(Y, U) \\ &- 2\eta(Y)\eta(U)g(X, Z), \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

where $(R(X, Y) \cdot S)(Z, U) = -S(R(X, Y)Z, U) - S(Z, R(X, Y)U)$ for all vector fields X, Y, Z and U on M . If possible, we suppose that $\bar{R} \cdot \bar{S} = R \cdot S$, then (4.1) gives

$$\begin{aligned} -g(X, Y)S(X, U) - 2(n+1)g(Y, Z)g(X, U) + 2\eta(Y)\eta(Z)g(X, U) \\ -g(Y, U)S(Z, X) + 2g(X, Z)S(Y, U) + 2(n+1)g(X, Z)g(Y, U) \\ - 2\eta(Y)\eta(U)g(X, Z) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Changing Y and U by ξ in (4.2) and then using the equations (2.1), (2.2), and (2.6), we obtain

$$S(Z, X) = -2ng(Z, X), \quad r = -2n(2n+1), \quad (4.3)$$

which shows that the Kenmotsu manifold endowed with a non-symmetric non-metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$, under assumption is an Einstein manifold. Also, from equations (3.7) and (4.3), we find

$$\bar{S}(Z, X) = 2g(Y, Z) - 2\eta(Y)\eta(Z). \quad (4.4)$$

This reflects that the Kenmotsu manifold M w.r.t. $\tilde{\nabla}$ under consideration is an η -Einstein manifold. Thus, we can state:

Theorem 4.1. *Let (M, g) be a $(2n+1)$ -dimensional Kenmotsu manifold equipped with a non-symmetric non-metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$. If $\bar{R} \cdot \bar{S} = R \cdot S$ on M , then the manifold to be an Einstein manifold also, M is an η -Einstein with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$.*

With the help of (4.3), equation (3.9) takes the form $\tilde{r} = 4n$, which shows that if a Kenmotsu manifold equipped with $\tilde{\nabla}$ satisfies $\bar{R} \cdot \bar{S} = R \cdot S$, then the scalar curvature with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$ is constant. Thus, we state:

Corollary. *If a $(2n+1)$ -dimensional Kenmotsu manifold M endowed with $\tilde{\nabla}$ satisfies $\bar{R} \cdot \bar{S} = R \cdot S$, then the scalar curvature of M with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$ to be constant.*

Arslan et al. (2014) proved that

“A semi-Riemannian Einstein manifold M of dimension $n, \geq 4$, satisfies

$$R \cdot C - C \cdot R = \frac{r}{n(n-1)}Q(g, R) = \frac{r}{n(n-1)}Q(g, C), \quad (4.5)$$

where $Q(g, R)$ denotes the Tachibana tensor and C is the conformal curvature tensor.”

From (4.3) and (4.5), we have

$$C \cdot R - R \cdot C = Q(g, R) = Q(g, C). \quad (4.6)$$

Thus, we state:

Corollary. *If a $(2n+1)$ -dimensional Kenmotsu manifold M equipped with $\tilde{\nabla}$ satisfies $\bar{R} \cdot \bar{S} = R \cdot S$, then M satisfies the equation (4.6).*

REFERENCES

- [1] N. S. Agashe & M. R. Chafle (1992). A semi-symmetric non-metric connection in a Riemannian manifold. Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 23, 399-409.
- [2] K. Arslan, R. Deszcz, R. Ezentas, M. Hotlos & C. Murathan (2014). On generalized Robertson-Walker space times satisfying some curvature condition. Turk J Math, 38, 353-373.
- [3] D. E. Blair (1976). Contact manifolds in Riemannian Geometry. Lecture Notes in Mathematics, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 509.
- [4] M. M. Boothby & R. C. Wong (1958). On contact manifolds. Anna. Math. 68, 421-450.
- [5] S. K. Chaubey & R. H. Ojha (2008). On semi-symmetric non-metric and quarter-symmetric metric connections. Tensor N. S., 70 (2), 202-213.
- [6] S. K. Chaubey, J. W. Lee & S. Yadav (2019). Riemannian manifolds with a semi-symmetric metric P-connection. J. Korean Math. Soc., 56 (4), 1113-1129.
- [7] O. Cihan & U. C. De (2006). On the quasi-conformal curvature tensor of a Kenmotsu manifolds. Mathematica Pannonica, 17 (2), 221-228.
- [8] U. C. De & G. Pathak (2004). On 3-dimensional Kenmotsu manifolds. Indian J. Pure Appl. Math., 35, 159-165.
- [9] U. C. De, A. Yildiz & Funda Yaliniz (2008). On ϕ -recurrent Kenmotsu manifolds, Turk J. Math., 32, 1-12.
- [10] U. C. De (2008). On ϕ -symmetric Kenmotsu manifolds. International Electronic J. of Geom., 1 (1), 33-38.

- [11] A. Friedmann & J. A. Schouten (1924). Uber die Geometrie der halbsymmetrischen Ubertra-gungen. Math. Z., 21 (1), 211-223.
- [12] J. B. Jun, U. C. De & G. Pathak (2005). On Kenmotsu manifolds. J. Korean Math. Soc., 42, 435-445.
- [13] K. Kenmotsu (1971). A class of almost contact Riemannian manifolds. Tohoku Math. J., 24, 93-103.
- [14] S. K. Chaubey & R. H. Ojha (2010). On the m -projective curvature tensor of a Kenmotsu manifold. Differential Geometry-Dynamical Systems, 12, 52-60.
- [15] S. K. Chaubey, S. Prakash & R. Nivas (2012). Some properties of m -projective curvature tensor in Kenmotsu manifolds. Bulletin of Math Analysis and Applications, 4, 48-56.
- [16] S. K. Chaubey & R. H. Ojha (2012). On a semi-symmetric non-metric connection. Filomat, 26 (2), 269-275.
- [17] S. K. Chaubey & C. S. Prasad (2015). On generalized ϕ -recurrent Kenmotsu manifolds, TWMS J. App. Eng. Math., 5 (1), 1-9.
- [18] S. K. Chaubey & A. Kumar (2010). Semi-symmetric metric T-connection in an almost contact metric manifold. International Mathematical Forum, 5 (23), 1121-1129.
- [19] S. K. Chaubey, A. C. Pandey & N. V. C. Shukla (2018). Some properties of Kenmotsu manifolds admitting a semi-symmetric non-metric connection, arXiv:1801.03000v1 [math.DG].
- [20] S. K. Chaubey & U. C. De (2019). Lorentzian para-Sasakian manifolds admitting a new type of quarter-symmetric non-metric ξ -connection. International Electronic Journal of Geometry, 12 (2), 266-275.
- [21] S. K. Chaubey & A. Yildiz (2019). Riemannian manifolds admitting a new type of semisymmetric nonmetric connection. Turk. J. Math., 43, 1887-1904.
- [22] B. B. Sinha & A. K. Srivastava (1991). Curvatures on Kenmotsu manifold. Indian J. Pure Appl. Math., 22 (1), 23-28.
- [23] S. K. Yadav, S. K. Chaubey & D. L. Suthar (2018). Certain results on almost Kenmotsu (κ, μ, ν) -spaces. Konuralp Journal of Mathematics, 6 (1), 128-133.
- [24] S. K. Chaubey & U. C. De (2019). Characterization of the Lorentzian para-Sasakian manifolds admitting a quarter-symmetric non-metric connection. SUT Journal of Mathematics, 55 (1), 53-67.
- [25] S. K. Chaubey & S. Yadav (2018). Study of Kenmotsu manifolds with semi-symmetric metric connection. Universal Journal of Mathematics and Applications, 1 (2), 89-97.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

is working as a faculty member in the Section of Mathematics, Department of Information Technology, College of Computing and Information Sciences, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Shinas, Sultanate of Oman. He received his Ph. D. degree in Pure Mathematics from Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, India in 2008. His research interests include differential geometry of differentiable manifolds, semi-Riemannian manifolds, linear connections and their applications. He is the member of Editorial boards for many reputed journals in his research areas. He has reviewed manuscripts for more than 60 journals and contributed many research publications in reputed journals.</p> <p>Orcid : https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3882-4596</p> <p>Scholar google: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=_rHMU4IAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=ao</p> <p>Research gate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/S-Chaubey</p>	
	<p>Mahesh Garvandha is a faculty member at University of Technology and Applied Sciences-Shinas, Sultanate of Oman. He possesses his M.Sc. (Mathematics and Scientific Computing) from National Institute of Technology, Warangal, India, and obtained his M.Tech (Computer Science and Engineering) from JNTU Hyderabad, and received his Ph.D. in Applied Mathematics from GITAM (Deemed to be University), India. His research interests include fluid dynamics, heat and mass transfer, nanofluids, differential geometry. He is a life time member of the Andhra Pradesh and Telangana Society of Mathematical Sciences. He has published research papers in international journals. He can be contacted at email: mahi.nit2003@gmail.com</p>
	<p>Sunil Kumar Yadav received the bachelor degree B.Sc. from DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh in 2004 and the Master degree M.Sc. in Mathematics from DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh in 2006 and the Doctor of Philosophy in Differential geometry from DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh in 2010. He is currently working as an Assistant Professor at United Collage of Engineering & Research, Naini, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh. He has published many research papers in various National and International Indexed Journals, including SCI, Wos, and Scopus. In addition he has authored of book "A text book of Operation Research" and book chapter "Lectures of pure mathematics on algebra, analysis and geometry". He can be contacted at email: prof_sky16@yahoo.com</p>